

Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin	Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin
Gopal Prasad	G:778 II	1.8	Bilaspur	Kanak	K:1741	2.4	Shahdol
Girmit	G:570	1.7	Balaghat	Barhi	B:1253 I	2.2	Mandla
Girmit	G:572	2.7	Balaghat	Barhi	B:1253 II	2.5	Mandla
Kansari	K:1761	1.1	Sidhi	Hiranakhi	H:161	2.8	Mandla
Galra	G:718	2.5	Sidhi	Basmati	B:409	2.6	Hoshangabad
Gadur Sela	G:699	0.6	Rajnandgaon	Wasmati	W:9 I	0.6	Muraina
Gadur Sela	G:701	2.9	Rajnandgaon	Kakadisar	K:544	2.8	Seoni
Ganja Kali	G:702	2.2	Rajnandgaon	TN1 (susceptible check)		9.0	
Kari Barhi	K:666	2.8	Rajnandgaon	Ptb33 (resistant check)		1.8	

^aBased on SES.

found resistant to BPH (see table). Most of them are from Bastar and Raipur districts. Results indicate that the germplasm maintained at MPRRI (about

Stress tolerance— excess water

Amount of volatile aldehydes released by rice plants after submergence

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During the initial phase of rice seed germination, the production of volatile aldehydes is significantly lower in high-vigor seeds than in medium- and low-vigor seeds.

We conducted an experiment to learn if a relationship exists between plant volatile aldehyde production and submergence tolerance. Seedlings of 10 rice varieties (see table) with varying degrees of submergence tolerance based on seedling survival were grown under greenhouse conditions. At 70 d after seeding, they were completely submerged for 6 d.

To determine aldehyde production, a 50-ml beaker containing 10 ml of 0.2% (wt/vol) 3-methyl-2-benzothiazolinone-hydrozone (MBTH) was placed inside a larger bottle containing a 5-g sample of chopped tissues from nonsubmerged and submerged plants. Each bottle was fitted

with an airtight screw cap to prevent gas leaks.

After 48 h, volatile aldehyde trapped by the aldehyde-absorbing reagent MBTH was determined. A 3-ml aliquot of MBTH was collected from each bottle, put into a test tube containing 2.5 ml of 0.23% (wt/vol) ferric chloride solution, and incubated for 10 min. We then added

20,000 accessions) is a rich source of resistance to BPH.

An insect-feeding test on bromocresol-treated filter paper was also

with an airtight screw cap to prevent gas leaks. After 48 h, volatile aldehyde trapped by the aldehyde-absorbing reagent MBTH was determined. A 3-ml aliquot of MBTH was collected from each bottle, put into a test tube containing 2.5 ml of 0.23% (wt/vol) ferric chloride solution, and incubated for 10 min. We then added

conducted. Insect feeding was judged by the amount of honeydew deposited by a female in 24 h on resistant cultivars Hinga, Kappe, Dhouri 1043, Dhouri 1163, Jaybay Rang, Khatia Pati, Kanak, Ganja Kali, Hiranakhi, and EB 17. Feeding rate was 0.17-65 mm² per female in 24 h, which was much lower than the 173-235 mm² per female feeding on TN1. On the resistant check PTB33, the rate was 49 mm² per female.

Hinga 435 and Dhouri 1043 had low plant damage scores and feeding rates of 65 and 53 mm² per female, respectively, suggesting that the genotypes have the ability to maintain vigor at those feeding rates. However, no correlation between plant damage score and feeding rate on Minga 435 and Dhouri 1043 was observed. ■

2.5 ml of absolute acetone to the tube and closed it with a tightly fitting cork. After 30 min, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was read at 635 nm. Formaldehyde solutions were used as standards.

The results showed that tissues from previously submerged plants released 0-8 times more volatile aldehydes than tissues from nonsubmerged plants.

Amount of volatile aldehydes produced by 70-d-old rice plants after 6 d submergence.

Variety	Survival (%) ^a	Volatile aldehydes produced (ml gas/100 g)		
		Submerged (control)	Submerged for 6 d	Increase over control ^b (%)
<i>Submergence-tolerant</i>				
FR13A (check)	80	16.0	21.0	5.0 (31)
Sabita	75	9.0	14.0	5.0 (55)
<i>Moderately submergence-tolerant</i>				
Sureh	65	4.1	17.0	12.9 (309)
Patnai 23	60	4.3	4.5	0.2 (4)
Jogen	45	4.3	21.4	17.1 (396)
Mahsuri	45	18.4	28.8	10.4 (56)
<i>Submergence-susceptible</i>				
Pankaj	40	4.0	17.0	13.0 (329)
Swarnadhan	35	18.4	32.1	13.7 (75)
Biraj	35	13.3	21.2	7.9 (59)
IR42 (check)	25	5.4	42.5	37.1 (687)
Mean	50	9.7	22.0	12.2
SE	5.5	1.9	3.1	3.0
LSD (0.05)	28	9.5	16.1	15.5

^aData taken after 12 d complete submergence at 60 DAT. ^bFigures in parentheses are percentages.

Tissues of IR42 that had been exposed to submerged conditions released the most aldehyde of all the samples (see table).

The correlation coefficients (r^2) between survival percentage and amount of aldehyde produced after submergence

was 0.64^{*}; that between survival percentage and increase in aldehyde production was 0.66^{**}. The significant negative relationship between survival percentage and aldehyde production after submergence ($y = 40.24 - 0.36x$) might

be useful in identifying superior donors for submergence tolerance.

Future research will include determining the types of volatile aldehydes produced by rice plants during submergence. ■

Stress tolerance— adverse temperature

Physiological screening of rice for low temperature tolerance

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A potential way to increase the tolerance of the rice plant for cold damage is to breed for cold-tolerant varieties. This requires a rapid and reliable way to identify cold-tolerant parents for use in a breeding program. This study evaluated the relationship between the amount of bleeding sap from the main rice culm and cold tolerance of cultivars. We also tried to establish the amount of sap as a criterion for cold tolerance selection in rice.

Twelve japonica rice cultivars were grown in 4-liter plastic pots that each had 3.5 kg soil (0.4 g N, 0.1 g P, and 0.2 g K

Relationship among bleeding sap of seedlings, spikelet filling, and grain weight.

Effect of low temperature treatment (15 °C) on the amount of bleeding sap from the main culm and relative percent reduction of spikelet filling of rice plants grown in a phytotron.^a

Variety	Amount of bleeding sap (g/cm ² per d) after various days of cold treatment									Cold tolerance score ^b	Fertility (%) at 25-30 °C	Fertility (%) at 15 °C	Relative reduction (%)
	1	2	3	4	5	6	Av						
Lijanxingtuanhegu	2.9 c	2.7 c	2.6 b	2.7 a	2.5 b	2.5 b	2.7 a	2	78	69	12		
Panlong 1	3.5 c	3.8 b	2.3 b	1.7 c	1.3 d	2.2 b	2.5 a	2	77	62	20		
Zhaotongmarxiegu	3.1 c	2.9 c	2.6 b	2.1 b	3.2 a	3.3 a	2.9 a	2	80	61	23		
Kunmingxiaobeigu	4.0 b	3.0 c	1.6 c	1.9 b	1.1 d	1.4 d	2.2 b	2	81	67	17		
Banjimang	4.7 a	3.8 b	2.5 b	2.0 b	2.0 c	2.6 b	3.0 a	3	75	58	22		
Gendiao 3	4.0 b	5.6 a	2.1 b	0.7 e	0.9 d	1.2 d	2.4 a	2	72	66	20		
Yungen 9	4.4 b	4.0 b	3.0 a	2.0 b	0.5 e	1.8 c	2.6 a	3	90	57	37		
79-219	3.5 c	2.2 d	1.3 c	1.5 c	1.3 d	1.3 d	1.8 c	5	71	17	76		
Shomewakai	2.1 d	1.6 e	1.4 c	2.4 a	1.9 c	1.9 c	1.9 c	5	96	24	75		
Yomaxiro	3.0 c	2.7 c	1.6 c	0.6 e	1.2 d	0.8 e	1.7 c	6	96	19	81		
Towata	2.4 d	1.5 e	0.7 d	0.8 e	0.3 e	1.6 c	1.2 d	7	96	5	95		
Nihonbarai	1.1 d	0.9 f	1.3 c	1.0 d	1.2 d	0.9 e	1.1 d	8	93	6	94		
Mean	3.2	2.9	1.9	1.6	1.5	1.8	2.1	3.9	85	42	48		

^aWithin columns, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 0.05 level by DMRT. ^bBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice*, (IRRI, 1980), where a score of 1 = most tolerant and 9 = most sensitive at seedling stage.